

DIGITAL ECONOMY IS A SHORT WAY TO PROGRESS

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Abstract. Nowadays, techniques and technologies are developing more and more. In this article, the relevance of changes in accounting in the context of the digitalization of the economy and its industries and the introduction of new techniques and technologies, the need to search for new management technologies, to achieve and form a competitive advantage, is described. The introduction of cloud technologies in the field of accounting is proposed to improve its efficiency and prevent errors. The advantages and disadvantages of these technologies are described in the basic principles of work, as well as in their analysis.

Keywords: economy, digital economy, digitalization, digital technologies, digital economy, digitalization, accounting, cloud technologies, database, information technologies.

ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА — КОРОТКИЙ ПУТЬ К ПРОГРЕССУ

Аннотация. В настоящее время техники и технологии развиваются все больше и больше. В данной статье описывается актуальность изменений в бухгалтерском учете в условиях цифровизации экономики и ее отраслей и внедрения новых методик и технологий, необходимость поиска новых технологий управления, достижения и формирования конкурентного преимущества. . Предлагается внедрение облачных технологий в сфере бухгалтерского учета для повышения его эффективности и предотвращения ошибок. Преимущества и недостатки этих технологий описаны в основных принципах работы, а также в их анализе.

Ключевые слова: экономика, цифровая экономика, цифровизация, цифровые технологии, цифровая экономика, цифровизация, учет, облачные технологии, база данных, информационные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

Today, technology and technologies are developing so much that there are no areas that have not been penetrated, walls that have not been occupied. Of course, it also entered the field of economics, and we discovered a new economy. We call this economy the digital economy. The digital economy is an economic activity in which the main factor in production and service is information in the form of numbers, with the help of processing a large amount of information and analyzing the result of this processing. is to implement more effective solutions than the previous system in production, service, technologies, devices, storage, product delivery. In other words, the digital economy is an activity connected with the development of digital computer technologies in the provision of online services, electronic payments, internet trade, crowdfunding and other types of fields. The concept of digital economy was defined not so long ago, in 1995, by Nicholas Negroponte, an American scientist from the University of Massachusetts. The scientist mentioned what changes may occur during the transition from the old economy to the new economy after the intensive development of information and communication technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Recently, the concept of "digital economy" has been used a lot. Indeed, in many developed countries, the digital economy has significantly influenced their development factors. The digital economy plays an important role in the life of society.

So this article will be about the digital economy. We will try to find answers to such important questions as "What is the digital economy?", "Tasks and goals of the digital economy", "Obstacles in the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan".

Before covering this topic, let's look at a situation that can happen in our daily life. Imagine that you came home from work on Friday, you are in the company of your family members, and you suddenly have the idea to travel by car to the Samarkand region and the city of Samarkand on Saturday and Sunday. But you don't have your own car. Then you entered the websites or mobile applications of car rental companies through your computer or smartphone, entered your name, driver's license number and ordered a family car for 6 people for two days. Now you need to choose the direction of travel. Where to go, which museum, historical monuments to visit. Then you enter the sites or mobile applications of agencies that provide travel services, enter the number of your family members and choose a tourist destination that is interesting for you and your family members. Then on Saturday morning you will have a 6-seater car in front of your house, tickets to museums and historical sites on your smartphone, and a pre-booked place to stay at a hotel. You organized a trip in the family car for two days without going anywhere or calling anyone. Then you went to Samarkand. After being there for two days, you feel a little tired when you come home on Sunday, and you have to go to work on Monday. Then you take your smartphone and immediately buy tickets for Afrosiyab high-speed trains for yourself and your family members, go to the station and go home, the car will be left at the station. E-commerce, internet banking, electronic payments, internet advertising and, at the same time, internet games are seen as the main elements of the development of the digital economy.

RESULTS

Due to the development and implementation of information technologies, many conveniences are appearing in our daily life. Let's say we want to eat, but we don't want to prepare it, it's not a problem, we can order the food we want online through the Internet home delivery service. Or we need to transfer money to a friend, in which there is no need to go to the bank or financial institution, we can transfer money through mobile banking. We can provide many of these services online, via smartphone or computer.

Following the development of digital technologies, a person can use the service he needs faster, save a lot of money by buying the products he needs cheaply through the Internet. For example, buying a book in electronic form can cost you much less than buying the same book in printed form. Otherwise, an ordinary consumer can become an entrepreneur himself and engage in online sales without leaving his home.

- increasing labor productivity in production;
- increasing the competitiveness of companies;
- reduction of production costs;
- creation of new jobs;
- emergence of new modern professions;
- overcoming poverty and eliminating social inequality.

The role of the state in the digital economy - as a result of studying the world experience, it became clear that in countries with a developed digital economy, in the digital economy, the

state (government) determines the rules of the market "game" for all participants of the game, and the most important role of the state in this as creating the same, equal rights and opportunities for the participants of the game. That is, whether it is a large company or a small business in the market, they are equal. They are given the same opportunities. It ensures that government regulations are followed and that, ultimately, the average consumer receives a quality, up-to-date service or product. Therefore, for the development of the digital economy, the state should create equal conditions for everyone, market rules, laws, contracts should be transparent as much as possible, laws should be based on market demand (that is, it should be able to determine development trends in the market in advance and adopt the necessary regulatory documents). it is necessary to provide freedom for the participants of the game.

Digital economy in Uzbekistan, like the countries of the world, the digital economy is developing in Uzbekistan. After the application of information technologies in our daily life, many opportunities are created for ordinary people. Nowadays, we can order many food products and meals without leaving home and have them delivered to our home. But it should be noted that the digital economy in Uzbekistan is developing several times slower than the potential of Uzbekistan. That is, there is an opportunity, the necessary resources are available, but the development is rather slow. As a reason for this, several obstacles to the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan can be pointed out:

- 1) monopoly in many areas;
- 2) low internet speed and poor quality;
- 3) that legislation in the field of information technologies is behind the times;
- 4) extremely low level of computer literacy among citizens;
- 5) non-transparency of legislation;
- 6) lack of information technology specialists or their departure to other countries;
- 7) low information culture, information hygiene;
- 8) information technology security is not good;
- 9) lack of specialists who understand the field in management bodies or (in some cases) their absence at all.

If the above-mentioned problems are solved gradually, systematically, based on world experience, Uzbekistan can easily become one of the countries with a developed digital economy.

Olimjon Umarov, the First Deputy Minister of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, said that the digital economy is not a separate type of activity, but the active use of information technologies in business, industrial facilities, and services. If material goods are considered the main resource in the ordinary economy, in the digital economy it is information and data that can be processed and transmitted.

According to the results of the analyzes conducted by the prestigious international organizations, the digital economy will increase the gross domestic product by at least 30%, therefore, it will end the secret economy, - says Eldor TULYAKOV, executive director of the "Strategy of Development" center. - If we turn to international practice, today the digital economy is not limited to the field of e-commerce and services, but to every aspect of life, in particular, health care, science and education, construction, energy, agriculture and water management, transport, geology, cadastre, archives, internet banking and other areas, and is

showing high results in each of them. The government's provision of electronic services and electronic products for its citizens is a key part of the digital economy. Broad development of this sector in our country will end the scourge of corruption.

The development and implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" program in Uzbekistan, first of all, the formation of thorough and perfect organizational and legal mechanisms, in addition, ensuring the harmonious cooperation of state bodies and business entities on the introduction of innovative ideas, technologies and developments, all spheres and covering production and service provision in networks with digital technologies, cultivating intellectually capable personnel with deep knowledge of modern knowledge, thereby serving to create an environment of "informed society" in the country.

Despite the presence of Click, Payme, M-bank, Upay, Oson and other payment systems that allow online payments, the rate of online payments for mobile payments, internet, and utility payments is not high. In 2017

34 percent of account holders made digital payments. By comparison, this figure is 96% in the UK. It is noteworthy that the number of payments through the terminal is increasing. For example, in 2018, payments through the terminal amounted to 53 trillion soums.

The concepts of digitization and cyber security always go hand in hand. Because along with the digitization of all systems and processes, it is important to ensure their technically perfect and error-free operation and safety. The more attention is paid to the development of the digital economy in our country, the more urgent it is to ensure cyber security. Uzbekistan is strengthening its position in the global cyber security index. In 2017, our country took 93rd place in this rating, and in 2018 it rose to 52nd place.

Cyber security is a form of information security and is a different concept than high spirituality that serves to sort out information. It refers to more technical processes, for the average user, it means setting up reliable and strong passwords in mail, social networks, payment systems, and protecting his personal computer and smartphone from viruses. In a broader sense, cyber security is a set of measures aimed at protecting networks, mobile applications and devices. This means maintaining the confidentiality of data, protecting their integrity, and the full operation of this or that site, application, or program.

According to the analysis of the "Cybersecurity Center" SUK, in 2019, 268 cyber security incidents were detected on the websites of the national segment of the Internet. This means that the number of crimes in the digital world has decreased by 44% compared to the previous year. Of these, 222 were related to unauthorized uploading of content, 45 to deface (a hacking attack that means a website page is replaced with another, such as an ad page), and one to stealth mining (hidden activity on a cryptocurrency platform).

As a result of monitoring the national segment of the Internet, more than 130,000 threats to cyber security have been identified. Of these, 106,508 cases relate to hosts that became participants in botnet networks. 13,882 cases involved blocking IP addresses blacklisted by various services due to spam email or password breaches. 8,457 cases are related to the use of the TFTP (Trivial File Transfer Protocol) protocol and related ports, which can lead to the download of extraneous content due to the lack of authentication mechanisms. 2,114 cases are related to the use of a vulnerable RDP (Remote Desktop Protocol) protocol. 1,042 cases are related to software and database management systems not having an authentication mechanism, as well as SSL-certificates with expired or invalid signatures.

These analyzes once again confirm the relevance of the issue of cyber security, because software vulnerabilities can cause an attacker to remotely access an information system or website, as well as files and data, and leak personal data of citizens. Cyber security measures prevent such situations.

National cyber security strategy for 2020-2023 and the draft law "On cyber security" according to the state program on the implementation of the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy Development" will be developed.

DISCUSSION

Judging from the above information, we can see that the economy is one of the most necessary areas for us. But we need to realize that we need to digitize it in order to develop it. That is, if we digitize it, we will achieve maximum efficiency. This means that we achieve maximum profit while minimizing costs. The digital economy expands the capabilities of a modern accountant, increases the quality and speed of accounting, and forms modern innovative approaches to the integration of various accounts. With the help of personal computers and special accounting programs, the replacement of paper work with automated accounting has made it possible to free the accountant from routine work and improve their work results.

CONCLUSIONS

Today, special Internet services have appeared that allow the production of all online accounting operations, banks and information technology portfolios that apply to the daily activities of an accountant. Cloud technology is a service for renting space on the Internet for storing and processing information. Cloud technologies have enough advantages to be used for accounting, but there are also disadvantages, the main part of which is an uninterrupted Internet connection.

Changes in technology have led to a change in accounting, which requires scientists and practitioners to formulate basic conceptual models, develop legislation, regulations, guidelines and regulations for accounting in the new digital economy.

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